

LEGAL TECHNOLOGY ON MODERN LEGAL PRACTICE

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Annotation

The scientific article reflects information about the place and role of legal tech - modern legal technology in legal practice, its history, current stage of development and perspective. There also has published scientific opinions on the introduction of modern information technology in jurisprudence.

Key words

legal tec, artificial intelligence, IT, big data, blockchain, cyber justice

It is known that modern technologies do not stand still, especially in the 21st century, they are rapidly developing. In the context of today's globalization, IT development has a dramatic impact on the economic growth of countries. Nowadays, many expressions such as "Digital Economy", "Blockchain", "Internet of things", "Artificial intelligence", "Big Data" are used by modern people. became an integral part of his life. IT covers every aspect of our daily life.

Legal Tech is a new field of science created by combining the fields of jurisprudence and information technologies, covering the legal field with digital technologies, providing automated legal services, and solving legal issues with the help of digital technologies. Currently, this field is introducing the following advanced technologies to jurisprudence:

- artificial intelligence;
- "big data" large data;
- automated legal service;
- robot lawyers;
- "cyber justice" digital court;
- blockchain technology;
- "smart contract" smart contract;
- modern legal instruments.

Automated legal services are becoming popular with the principles of saving time, financial resources, and convenient operation for clients. Smaller organizations usually cannot afford to pay for a separate lawyer. These services are very relevant for small business representatives. There are more than ten automated legal tech tools in the Russian legal services market alone. We can include the following among them: "Pravo.ru", "Consultant+", "Garant", "FreshDoc", "48Prav.ru", "Pravoved.ru". One of the country's leading banks, Sberbank, has replaced more than 3,000 lawyers with automated legal services software.

Experts say that automated legal service tools can do almost 70 percent of a lawyer's work[10]. For example, one of the world's famous financial organizations, JP Morgan, has applied to its activities by creating a software that performs in a few seconds what lawyers do in 360 hours. Another IT giant, IBM Corporation, has developed software that saves lawyers' time by 50 percent. Currently, modern legal tech tools are becoming popular in developed countries, including "Rocket Lawyer", "legalzoom", "LegalOnline", "lexmachina.com", "hireanesquire.com", "casetext.com" and a number of other advanced technological programs. will be An example of the above is a special online program aimed at ensuring that a person who violates the traffic rules in Canada and is dissatisfied with the fine issued by the police can go to court without the help of a lawyer and ensure that his case is processed in a short period of time. It is also possible to single out programs such as legal disputes, finding the norms of legal documents applicable to problems, conducting examination of contracts.

Also, in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2020 "On measures to further improve the activities of judicial bodies and institutions in the implementation of the state legal policy" No. implementation and digitalization of public services is intended to launch the "virtual justice" system.

In addition, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6079 dated October 10, 2020 "On approval of the Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy and measures for its effective implementation" on the sphere of public administration in our country development, in particular, further expansion of high-quality and high-demand electronic state services at the country level, step-by-step transfer of all state services to digital form is envisaged.

In accordance with Appendix 1 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan Resolution No. 409 of June 25, 2020, the "E-Government Project Management Center" state institution under the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan

"Introduction of digital technologies in public administration and justice bodies" department" is operating.

In accordance with the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 17, 2021 "On measures to create conditions for the rapid introduction of artificial intelligence technologies" No. PQ-4996 under the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development A scientific-research institute for the development of digital technologies and artificial intelligence was established. In paragraph 14 of the program of measures for the study and implementation of artificial intelligence technologies in 2021-2022 of this decision, the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development, the Ministry of Innovative Development, the Academy of Sciences and Higher and Secondary Special Education Development of an explanatory dictionary on artificial intelligence in the State language by the Ministry of Education, and holding "hackathons" and competitions in order to encourage researchers to write practical algorithms in the field of artificial intelligence is provided for in paragraph 15.

At this point, it is worth noting that in this Decision, the activity of joint research projects of national and foreign higher education institutions and scientific-research organizations in the field of artificial intelligence, the development of international scientific research activities aimed at the development of artificial intelligence, and the development of artificial intelligence It is also decided to send young scientists conducting research activities in the field of artificial intelligence to short-term foreign scientific internships. The regulatory legal document also provides for the introduction of crowd funding mechanisms for start-up projects in the field of artificial intelligence.

In Annex 6 of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4996 of February 17, 2021, the introduction of training courses and subjects on the practical application of artificial intelligence technologies in the economic sectors, social sphere and public administration system Tashkent State Law University is included in the list of higher educational institutions.

It should be noted that currently a number of scientific activities are being carried out in the field of legal tech, including the above-mentioned TDYU Legal Tech laboratory, S. Gulyamov's Cyberlaw.uz (<http://cyberlaw.uz/>) school of cyber law. , the Central Asia Tech Law (<https://centralasiatechlaw.com/>) project by Dr. Ammar Younas. In addition, the international conference on "Modern trends in the development of digitalization in the field of justice", held on December 15, 2021 by

the Legal Policy Research Institute under the Ministry of Justice, is aimed at researching the field of legal tech.

In addition, a number of developments related to legal technologies are operating in our country today: lex.uz, <https://advice.uz/uz>, <https://yurxizmat.uz/uz>.

However, there are a number of shortcomings that currently hinder the development of legal tech. These include:

1. Norms, road maps, and measures in the current legal documents related to digitization of jurisprudence remain in the document. Systematic control over their implementation is insufficient. The question of who should conduct systematic control remains open?

2. The analysis of the above normative legal documents shows that the measures aimed at the development of the legal tech sector are implemented in a scattered manner. In particular, the activities of the Ministry of Information and Communications, the Ministry of Justice, TDYU, the Research Institute for the Development of Digital Technologies and Artificial Intelligence, TATU are carried out without mutual agreement. A collective approach to this issue is necessary.

3. Scientific research aimed at the development of legal tech, results of scientific research, junction points of projects (platforms, circles, working groups) are almost non-existent. Each state organization, scientific research centers are conducting autonomous research. In particular, the IT Park, which is receiving a lot of attention in our country today, is questionable as to whether it is related to Legal tech directions in the 1 million coders projects.

4. A unified approach to the development of Legal tech projects has not been developed at the level of the Ministry of Justice and TDYU. It is necessary to draw up a road map with specific goals and tasks regarding this issue.

5. There is no clear distribution of the measures to be implemented based on each implemented project within the legal tech projects of the university. In each project, there should be a distribution of work between the participants.

6. The list of topics and directions of scientific research carried out and expected to be carried out in the field of legal tech has not been formed by the scientific department.

7. One of the important shortcomings is the fact that the support mechanism for any scientific and applied research, which should be carried out by scientific researchers, has not been revised based on a modern approach, and the mechanisms for stimulating their work have not been developed. For example: For

a specific part of a legal tech project, there is no defined allocation of funds for the work performed.

8. There are a number of administrative restrictions of the university to implement legal tech projects together with international experts. For example, a Pakistani specialist, who taught at the university for a year, had to appeal to the international department several times in his career for not receiving funds related to accounting on time.

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